
Impact of Gender Inequality of Economic Development

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Abstract:

Gender equality is essential for the realization of human rights and sustainable development. Because gender equality is the key to sustainable development. If there is equality between men and women, it is possible to establish many businesses and achieve equal opportunities for economic development and sustainable development is achieved. Through sustainable development, many individual ambitions will be fulfilled, many people's talents will be developed and equal opportunities will be achieved in education and in all fields. All women will be completely free from gender based violence. However, gender inequality still exists in our country and women are excluded or given less important and less responsible jobs in decision-making processes, workplaces and society. Empowerment of women is important if gender equality is to be promoted. Also gender needs to be mainstreamed. Gender mainstreaming aims to increase the empowerment of women in population and development activities. For this it is necessary to address the known gender inequality in areas such as division of labor by paying attention to both the social and economic status and location of women as well as men. Programs should be designed so that both women and men can participate fully as equal partners in private and social life. Gender equality does not only mean equality between men and women, but it also means empowering men and giving them important rights. Men have more family responsibilities, so many economic problems are faced by men, so men also need to be brought to the level of equality. If men do not get the right opportunity, they drink alcohol, or commit suicide. For this, the government should prepare a suitable draft plan by looking at the role and needs of men, the economic development of the country depends on both gender equality and sustainable development. This important point has to be acknowledged.

Keywords: *GBV- Gender- Based violence, UN - United Nations, GDP-Gross domestic Product, SDG- Sustainable Development Goals*

Importance:

Gender equality is not only a matter of justice and inclusive growth, but it is a prerequisite for sustainable development. Women play a key role in energy use, production and consumption, but they are still marginalized and face many barriers, which limit their participation in many areas. If the country wants to achieve sustainable development, first it is necessary to eliminate sexual violence against women and girls. Women are still victims of exploitation such as trafficking in women,

sexual exploitation, and financial exploitation, emotional and physical coercion. Also, child marriages of girls are still taking place. Women are deprived of education. To this end, the United Nations has emphasized gender equality in Sustainable Development Goal Five (S.D.G.5). Some of the targets for achieving Sustainable Development Goal 5 include the various forms of gender-based violence experienced by women around the world. These include forced marriage, child marriage, female genital mutilation as well

as physical, emotional, and financial coercion, where women are deprived of freedom of decision. Violence against women is a global problem. Although these harmful practices are decreasing but the ongoing efforts to eliminate all these practices by 2030 are not enough. For this, steps should be taken in the future by considering what exactly is the need of the country and what should be done to bring equality between men and women, and also prepare various plans and schemes. If there is to be a social revolution, a big plan must be created. It is necessary to find the root cause why women are exploited in many ways. Also measures should be taken to reduce this exploitation. Only if these measures are implemented, it can be said that sustainable development is taking place in the true sense. In the present article, the oppression of women, their causes, and measures to achieve equality between men and women have been discussed. If the people of the country are starving, their character is being violated, they are not getting jobs according to their education, their economic life properly. It will not work and they will remain dissatisfied. For this, a proper plan should be prepared considering the exact needs of men and women so that gender equality can be achieved and sustainable development can be achieved. Gender equality doesn't just mean women's empowerment, but what do men do to drive their economic careers? Are they happy in worldly life? How does their biography work? Do they get the right salary for their education from the government on time? What should be done for the educated unemployed need to get proper salary for their education? How is the standard of living of educated people? Are the farmers getting fair price for their produce? What is the standard of living of the farm laborer? This experience should also be included in this. Taking a holistic view of everything and finding solutions to

that problem is an important goal of sustainable development. For this, it is necessary to consider the latent resource wealth in the country. Equal rights to economic resources, property, and financial services should be given to women and men. Often the income earned by women is not counted in the national income. They are not given ownership of that income. Women are not given the right to inherit property in many areas. By increasing the use of technology, women in rural areas should be provided with various opportunities. If we want to change the society, it is not only the role of the government, but this change should happen from within ourselves, from the society itself. Everyone should be made aware of the equality of men and women.

Objectives:

1. To explore the relationship between sustainable development and gender equality
2. To study the Sustainable Development Goals in the context of gender equality.
3. To suggest solutions to reduce gender inequality.
4. To highlight the empowerment of women.

Gender Equality and Economic Development:

The World Bank Group's Accelerate Equality initiative has reviewed the progress made in reducing gender disparities over the past decade. It has made the following changes

Progress has been slow:

The World Bank Group published the World Development Report 2012: Gender Equality and Development. It found that maternal mortality rates have fallen by 10 percent and the number of girls in secondary school has increased by 5 percent. The Women's Business and Law Index

shows that women's economic rights have improved and that women's participation in national parliaments has increased worldwide. In many low-income countries, women's participation in the labor force is low and there is a gap in income. In many countries, women still accept low-paid jobs for fear of protection. Women take on especially caring for the elderly and domestic work. The World Bank Group reports that women are underrepresented in high-level leadership positions and are doing more. However, according to the Women's Business and Law Index, women's economic rights have improved and more women are now participating in national parliaments than ever before. Women are voluntarily moving forward, breaking away from traditional norms, changing their jobs, taking up male-dominated professions, and completing their education and becoming independent. The practice of early marriage is now decreasing. Also, violence against women and girls, including rape, is still increasing globally. Due to gender inequality, women cannot exercise their right to equal citizenship. Women have to follow many social rules. Customs, practices, and traditions hold women back from their responsibilities. A patriarchal culture still exists in rural as well as urban areas.

Growing Debt and Pandemic Challenges:

Violence against women and girls has increased due to the COVID-19 crisis. Women are more likely than men to lose their jobs in Latin America and the Caribbean. An estimated 11 million girls will not return to school due to the COVID-19 pandemic, according to a report by UN Women. Violence against women has intensified since the start of COVID-19. The available data on adolescent girls' return to school is alarming and a serious problem. Of the girls who did not return to school, 27% cited pregnancy as the reason for not

returning. This illustrates the violence against adolescent girls.

Investment Gives People A Way Forward:

If we want to create inclusive growth, equal society, and empowerment, we have to face the challenges of protecting women and girls, as well as investing. Gender equality does not only mean empowering women, but also empowering men. Men should also be empowered by providing them with appropriate work opportunities, fair wages, and opportunities. We should recognize the full potential of people and provide them with jobs according to their education. If gender equality is created in employment, GDP will be almost 20 percent higher. With quality education, healthcare, and security, people can better cope with shocks like climate change and economic crises. The needs of women and girls who face disadvantages like poverty, unemployment, migration, and disability should be addressed. Their problems should be solved.

Climate Change Impacts Women's Empowerment:

Climate change impacts economic opportunities for both men and women while implementing national policies and development strategies. Involving women in national policies is the key to economic development. Girls' education, family planning, reproductive health, reducing child marriage, and women's opportunities in leadership are important in women's empowerment. There needs to be a transformative change towards equality between men and women, for which concerted efforts are needed. This requires further changes in laws and policies. Now, society needs to accept climate change and take steps towards gender equality. Rather than the government bringing about change, all people need to change within themselves. Only then will equal economic opportunities

be available to women and men. Women should be encouraged to be adventurous.

Gender Equality And Social Inclusion Are Two Important Things To Create Sustainable Development:

Gender Equality:

Gender equality means equal rights, responsibilities and opportunities for women and men. There will be no discrimination in this. This means that women and men should have equal opportunities to shape their lives and participate in social processes by choosing the right opportunities, using the available resources. If this is the case, equality between women and men increases. The rights, responsibilities and opportunities given to each person will have nothing to do with gender, and every person should have equal opportunities, benefits in socio-economic and political terms, and should have equal access to every service.

Social Inclusion:

Social inclusion means increasing social awareness among people, as well as accepting social obligations, developing ourselves by remembering that we are a part of society, getting various opportunities, making full use of our abilities and finding a place in society and eliminating inequalities wherever they appear is an important part of inclusion. Gender equality and social inclusion are two very important aspects from the point of view of economic development. Economic policies and programs should be designed in such a way that all women, all men and excluded groups at the bottom do not have a way of worrying and everyone benefits and the needs of all are fulfilled. If sustainable development is to be achieved through gender equality, the contribution of every woman and man is necessary.

Gender Equality Facts: Sustainable Development Goal No. 5

The fifth of the UN's 17 Sustainable Development Goals is to achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls. Justice, dignity, health, and equal opportunities for all to achieve a future are important from a gender equality perspective. Here are some gender equality facts that explain the SDGs:

SDG Goal No. 5 Targets:

End All Forms Of Discrimination Against All Women And Girls Everywhere:

1. To measure this target, the success is measured by whether there is a legal framework for gender equality and non-discrimination on the basis of sex. In this regard, the World Bank has released the following statistics: According to the 2021 edition of "Women in Business and the Law", there are 88 countries that prevent women from working in some jobs. 49 countries do not have laws against domestic violence. 45 countries do not have laws against sexual harassment. And 112 countries are where marital rape is not a crime. These things confirm gender inequality. For this, it is necessary to formulate policies to protect women's rights in the home, workplace and public places. Only then will gender equality be achieved.
2. Another important UN goal is to end all forms of violence, trafficking and sexual and other forms of exploitation against all women and girls in the public and private sectors. This gender inequality is due to factors such as class, ethnicity, age, sexual orientation, disability status or culture, etc. GBV affects one in three women and girls, and is linked to crises such as gender inequality, poverty, conflict, and the COVID-19 lockdown. For example, the World Bank has ranked Pakistan among the lowest in the world in terms of gender equality, based on its background. According to a UN report, 70 to 90 percent of Pakistani women experience physical, emotional or

psychological abuse by a partner or intimate partner.

Covid-19:

As poverty levels have risen during the Covid-19 lockdown, many parents have forced their teenage daughters to marry off because they cannot afford to take care of their children. This has resulted in teenage girls missing out on their education, facing domestic violence at home and suffering for the rest of their lives. Premature births and deaths from these are on the rise among young girls. UNICEF estimates that this is particularly prevalent in sub-Saharan Africa, particularly in Niger, the African Union and Chad. UNICEF estimates that 21% of married women aged 20 to 24 were married before their 18th birthday. Every year, 12 million girls are married before they are legally adults. The good news is that many in South Asia have been prevented by laws and community participation, with 25 million child marriages prevented in the past decade.

Inclusion of Women's Domestic Work In GDP:

The fourth goal of Sustainable Development Goal 5 is to ensure that women do 2.6 times more paid and domestic work than men. That work should be included in GDP. It is necessary to include women in public service infrastructure and social protection policies, as well as to recognize and value domestic work. When women are able to work for pay in many sectors, economies are stronger. According to a report by the Making Sense Global Institute, if women played the same role as men in the labor market, the global annual GDP could be added by \$28 trillion, or 37 percent, by 2025. However, in many countries, due to patriarchal cultures, there is a perception that men's and women's work are different and this needs to change.

Globally, Women Make Up Only 25% of National Parliaments:

Research shows that governments are increasingly focusing on legislation that promotes gender equality. However, globally, women make up just 25% of national parliaments. Only four countries have at least 50% female representation in their legislative branches. These are the United Arab Emirates - 50%, Bolivia - 53%, Cuba - and Rwanda - 61%. Many challenges need to be addressed at the legislative level to increase gender equality, and more women need to be represented in policy-making.

Every Day, 808 Women Die Between Pregnancy and Childbirth:

That's one woman every two minutes, and according to the United Nations Population Division, an estimated 20 to 30 percent of women who die are injured during pregnancy and childbirth. These deaths are preventable through access to good maternal and child health care and access to family planning resources. Safe and voluntary family planning is a human right. However, the UN estimates that 218 million women in low-income countries do not have access to effective family planning methods, or that women who want to avoid pregnancy do not have access to them. This is because many cultures are patriarchal. Many women cannot go to the doctor without the permission of their husbands, fathers, or brothers, and do not have access to adequate medical facilities. This can be a dangerous environment for both mother and child.

Women Own Less Than 20% of The World's Land Because of Male-Dominated Inheritance Practices:

It is often seen that women can farm land but do not have ownership rights. This system must be changed to bring about gender equality. The fifth Sustainable Development Goal of the Sustainable

Development Goals is to ensure that women have equal rights to economic resources, land and other forms of property, in other types of service concessions, in government reservation in employment, and in ownership and control over natural resources. Many laws are being enacted in this regard.

However, many improvements are being made through technology and communication to promote women's empowerment. It is necessary to increase the number of health nurses in remote areas and provide them with mobile phones. Pregnant women and children should be protected with high-quality care. The future generation should be strengthened by taking special health care. If technology is used properly, the challenge of gender equality can be faced.

Importance of Gender Equality:

Gender equality is important for improving the economic condition of the country and eradicating poverty.

Educated Women Reduce Mortality Rates:

If a woman is educated, the risk of infant mortality is reduced by five to ten percent. If a woman completes secondary education, infant mortality is reduced by half. Also, if all mothers complete primary education, the maternal mortality rate will be reduced by two-thirds, and the health of women and children will improve. Women's education will prevent teenage pregnancy and child marriage.

Women's Labor Power Strengthens Economies:

According to a report by the Mexico Global Institute, if women played a role in the labor market, the global annual GDP could be added to \$28 trillion, or 26%, by 2025.

At the global level, women face many barriers to entering the labor market. According to UNESCO, more than 2.7 billion women are legally prohibited from

choosing the same jobs as men. In fact, women can work in many sectors along with men, which boosts the economy and also helps to provide for the family. This allows families to have access to education, adequate food, and other basic needs.

Gender Equality is Essential for Good Health:

Almost a thousand women die every day due to preventable causes related to pregnancy and childbirth. Inadequate health care facilities have a devastating impact on the family, and children of sick mothers are more likely to not receive health care. Older siblings are often left at home to care for their younger siblings, preventing them from attending school. Educational facilities are inadequate in rural areas, and children who drop out of school are often left behind. When women take proper care of their children, the health of the family is not affected. For this, women must first be educated. Not only does the family develop because of women, but society develops as a result.

If The Government Focuses On Gender Equality And Makes Laws In This Regard, It Will Improve The Legal System:

All forms of gender-based violence exist in all countries. Every culture treats men and women differently. For example, girls who marry at a young age do not get quality education. Also, child brides often face high levels of discrimination and violence, which is why the maternal mortality rate is high in many countries. Forced and early marriage is a major form of violence against women and girls. The government is helping through laws to change these customs and traditions. This will improve the legal system.

Women Are Less Likely To Re-Engage In Conflict If They Are Involved In Peace Talks:

The 2015 UN Women report on gender equality and conflict concludes that

“women’s participation is key to sustainable peace.” When women mediate or negotiate peace agreements, they are more likely to last.

To Break The Cycle Of Poverty, We Must First Break The Cycle Of Gender Inequality:

Gender inequality is a vicious cycle that endangers the lives of women and children and kills millions of mothers and children every year. Gender inequality is both a cause and a consequence of poverty and hunger. The World Food Programme estimates that 60% of the world's hungry are women and children, and the UN estimates that 70% of the 1.3 billion people living in poverty worldwide are women. The global estimated risk of a woman dying from maternal and child causes is one in 4,900. This figure rises to one in 180 in low-income countries. The sad reality is that these deaths are largely preventable, so the vicious cycle of gender inequality must be broken first.

The first and foremost human right is equality between men and women. It means that women, men, boys, girls of all classes and races participate equally in society and have equal value and rights. They have the right to access resources, freedom and opportunity. Gender equality is one of the main objectives of the United Nations Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The objective behind this is that men and women should be treated equally in social, economic and other aspects of society and should not be discriminated on the basis of their sex.

Linkage between Women’s Economic Empowerment and Sustainable Development:

Women’s economic empowerment is essential to promote sustainable development. The following issues are important in the context of women’s economic empowerment.

Women’s Right to Participate in Economic Decision-Making:

Enhancing women’s meaningful participation in economic decision-making at all levels, from the household to the international level, promoting women’s economic justice and economic rights, and closing the gender gap in the workplace are the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. And this is very important for achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. When more women work, economies grow, women’s incomes increase, women’s economic empowerment and income equality are achieved. Thus, closing the gender gap could provide a USD 7 trillion boost to the global economy.

Providing technical education to women and girls is important for their health and income opportunities, as well as for rapid technological change and sustainable development. It has also been observed that women perform better in senior management positions in many large companies. Many companies that utilize the intellectual potential of women are today very profitable. It has been observed that women have better organizational skills. Reducing gender inequality in industrial sectors will not only lead to economic empowerment of women but also achieve sustainable economic development.

Current Status of Women:

One in 10 women lives in extreme poverty. Gender inequalities in employment and job quality require the creation of social protection benefits that are earned through employment, such as pensions, unemployment benefits and maternity protection. Globally, an estimated 73.5% of women in paid employment do not have access to social protection. The gender gap in food insecurity has increased from 1.7% in 2019 to more than 4% in 2021. Lack of water and sanitation continues to plague women and girls, whether at home, school or

work. Women are less likely to have bank accounts in the financial sector. Globally, women's participation in internet use is very low, at just 37%.

Gender Differences in Law:

Gender disparities in the law affect women in both developing and developed economies. As of 2023, more than a third of the 190 economies (69 economies) have laws restricting women's decision to work. And 43 economies have no laws preventing sexual harassment in the workplace.

That is, the inclusion of women in the labor market is less than that of men. Also women are more likely to be unemployed than men. And women are overrepresented in informal and precarious employment. According to a 2018 research, globally nearly 60 percent of women are involved in the informal economy in terms of employment. This proportion is over 90% in low-income countries. In agriculture, women are overrepresented in seasonal informal part-time and low-wage jobs. Globally, in sub-Saharan Africa, 66 percent of women are employed in agri-food systems, compared to 47 percent in South Asia. 71 percent of female workers are involved in the agri-food system compared to male workers.

Women farmers are not given ownership rights over their productive assets. Globally, less than 15 percent of agricultural landholders are women. Reducing the gender gap in agricultural productivity could increase global gross domestic product by one percent. That is almost USD 1 trillion. Women are paid less than men. Women face many disadvantages while starting a new business, thus the potential of women to become entrepreneurs is low. Women face many barriers in the industrial sector.

Gender Norms:

Gender norms are rules about how men and women should behave, express themselves, and interact with others. Media, socialization, and culture contribute to the development of gender norms, and they vary by place and time. Gender socialization affects students. For example boys learn to be assertive, competitive, and independent while girls become emotional and disobedient. Research has shown that adherence to gender norms has a negative impact on children's mental health, social development, and academic performance.

Some examples of gender norms are as follows

Media: Many TV shows and movies portray male protagonists as strong, dominant and aggressive while women are portrayed as emotional and oppressed.

Education: Teachers treat boys and girls differently in school. In books or reading materials, men are portrayed as inventors and leaders while women are given passive roles. In school sports, male players are preferred while female teams are neglected.

Family: Parents have different expectations or set different rules for their children. For example, boys are given opportunities to pursue careers in different fields, while in the case of girls, raising a family and cultivating relationships, getting married early are given priority. Boys are given outdoor chores while girls are given domestic chores e.g. Jobs like cooking and cleaning are provided.

How to Break Gender Norms:

There are many misconceptions about gender and sexuality in society. It is possible to remove this misunderstanding only with the initiative of schools and society. A positive attitude of men towards women in Indian patriarchal culture should be inculcated in students through education. Family, society and school should create

awareness of gender equality among students.

Article 14, 15 (1 & 3), 16, 19, 21 (a), 26 (1) and 46 of the Constitution of India provide for gender equality and attempt to address gender inequality by referring to the constitutional provision. According to the National Education Policy 1986, the element of gender equality has been included in ten major core elements.

Major Findings:

1. Although significant progress has been made in recent years towards gender equality, women still face many barriers to participating in the economy on an equal footing with men.
2. Women's ability to earn a living is limited by multiple household responsibilities and lack of capital, digital tools, markets and childcare. Many jobs cannot be done by women due to social norms. Also low-income women especially face these barriers as some social norms prevent women from full participation
3. Women should come forward themselves in some fields,
4. But due to many types of fear, they cannot do new business. Also they do not get family support. Almost 50 percent of women have not participated in economic development.

Suggestion:

1. First gender inequality in all sectors should be reduced, and for this various government schemes should be adopted.
2. Increasing women's participation is important in terms of human capital and inclusive growth. If these women work in many sectors, the national income will increase and our economy will be strengthened.
3. Reducing inequality between Men and women must first begin with each family.
4. Laws regarding gender equality should be implemented, especially women should be exercise their rights. Men should also try to reduce patriarchal culture.

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